

Feasibility analysis of advanced indirect evaporative air-cooling systems in Mediterranean area climate

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Keywords: *annual assessment, desiccant system, dew-point efficiency, indirect evaporative cooling, Spain*

1. Introduction

Due to the ongoing rise in the global outdoor temperature, there is a necessity to develop efficient air-cooling systems capable of satisfying the increasing demand for cooling in buildings. In this context, evaporative cooling technologies could offer a sustainable alternative when compared to conventional direct expansion units (Romero-Lara, 2021). According to several research findings, indirect evaporative cooling (IEC) technology presents a sustainable solution for attaining thermal comfort, all the while decreasing energy consumption and reducing environmental consequences (Yang, 2021). However, it is important to analyse which technology is most suitable for each climate zone based on the outdoor air conditions.

The main objective of this work was to evaluate the feasibility of using two advanced air-cooling systems based on IEC technology: (i) Dew-point Indirect Evaporative Cooler (DIEC) and (ii) Desiccant Dew-point Indirect Evaporative Cooler (DW-DIEC), under the Cordoba and Malaga weather conditions, in Spain. Empirical models of the supply air temperature (T_{SA}) for both DIEC and DW-DIEC were used to calculate the dew-point efficiency (ϵ_{dp}). Annual values of the DIEC feasibility rate (FR_{DIEC}) and the DW-DIEC feasibility rate ($FR_{DW-DIEC}$) were also analysed for each selected city.

2. Material and methods

In this work, two experimental models were used to obtain the FR and ϵ_{dp} values for DIEC and DW-DIEC under the weather conditions of Cordoba and Malaga. The DW-DIEC system was mainly composed of a DIEC to control air temperature and a desiccant wheel (DW) to control air humidity. In a recent work, the authors detailed the main characteristics and experimental setup built to analyse the DIEC system performance (Romero-Lara, 2022). Then, several experimental tests were carried out under different working conditions to evaluate the DW-DIEC system performance, resulting in a

preliminary DW-DIEC empirical model with high value of coefficient of determination (R^2), 0.94. The T_{SA} model for DIEC showed good agreement, with a R^2 value of 0.93. For this work, the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems operated with a volumetric flow rate of inlet air of $3750 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and an exhaust air ratio (R) of 0.45, the nominal R value for DIEC.

Two Spanish cities in the Mediterranean area, Cordoba and Malaga, were selected to perform the DIEC and DW-DIEC assessment in terms of annual FR and ϵ_{dp} , see Figure 1. Different outdoor air (OA) conditions were shown due to the location of these cities: hot-dry climate for Cordoba and hot-humid climate for Malaga, see

Figure 2.

Figure 1. Location of Spanish selected cities.

Figure 2. Air temperature (T) and air humidity ratio (ω) for Spanish selected cities.

It can be observed that a case study was proposed where the required indoor air conditions were: $T_{\text{indoor}} = 26 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and $\omega_{\text{indoor}} = 12 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ (relative humidity of 57.03%). The set-points (SP) for SA conditions to the premises were: $T_{\text{SP}} = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $\omega_{\text{SP}} = 10.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. These SP values determined the feasibility of using the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems under the Cordoba and Malaga weather conditions. The annual FR values and the ε_{dp} values were calculated according to Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, respectively.

$$FR = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{Number of hours } T_{OA} > T_{SP}; \omega_{OA} < \omega_{SP}}{\text{Number of annual hours (8760 hours)}} & ; \text{ for DIEC} \\ \frac{\text{Number of hours } T_{OA} > T_{SP}}{\text{Number of annual hours (8760 hours)}} & ; \text{ for DW-DIEC} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{dp} = \frac{T_{OA} - T_{SA}}{T_{OA} - T_{SA,dp}} \quad (2)$$

3. Results and conclusions

A performance analysis based on feasibility rate (FR), supply air (SA) conditions and dew-point efficiency (ϵ_{dp}) for two advanced air-cooling systems, DIEC and DW-DIEC, were carried out in this work. The annual FR and ϵ_{dp} values were obtained according to Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, respectively, under the Cordoba and Malaga outdoor air conditions.

Figure 3 illustrates the annual feasibility of using DIEC under the Cordoba weather conditions, showing a rate of 33.5%. However, the annual FR_{DIEC} value under the Malaga weather conditions was 19.7%, due to the higher ω_{OA} values than for Cordoba. The FR values of using DW-DIEC were higher under Cordoba and Malaga OA conditions, 41.0% and 44.0%, respectively, due to the air humidity control of the desiccant wheel (DW), see Figure 3. The difference between $FR_{DW-DIEC}$ and FR_{DIEC} was higher for Malaga due to the higher ω_{OA} values.

Figure 3. Feasibility rate (FR) values for DIEC and DW-DIEC.

The annual period in which DIEC and DW-DIEC operated in ventilation mode (when $T_{OA} < T_{SP}$) was similar, 59.0% for Cordoba and 56.0% for Malaga. This was due to the similar number of hours in which T_{OA} was lower than 20 °C in both cities, see Figure 1.

The OA conditions of Cordoba and Malaga during periods in which DIEC and DW-DIEC operated can be observed in Figure 4 and Figure 5. The T_{OA} values for Cordoba were

between 20.01 °C and 43.78 °C, see Figure 4a and Figure 4b. The ω_{OA} values for Cordoba were between 4.06 g·kg⁻¹ and 12.62 g·kg⁻¹ when the DW-DIEC operated, see Figure 4b. However, the range of ω_{OA} values changed for DIEC due to the SP of 10.5 g·kg⁻¹. In this case, the ω_{OA} values were between 4.06 g·kg⁻¹ and 10.49 g·kg⁻¹, see Figure 4a. According to the Malaga weather conditions, the T_{OA} values ranged between 20.01 °C and 37.16 °C, as shown in Figure 5a and Figure 5b. The ω_{OA} values for Malaga were higher than for Cordoba, between 5.48 g·kg⁻¹ and 14.82 g·kg⁻¹ when the DW-DIEC operated, see Figure 5b. However, the range of ω_{OA} values for DIEC varied due to the SP of 10.5 g·kg⁻¹. In this other case, the ω_{OA} values ranged between 5.48 g·kg⁻¹ and 10.49 g·kg⁻¹, see Figure 5a.

The SA conditions of using DIEC and DW-DIEC under the Cordoba and Malaga weather conditions can also be observed in Figure 4 and Figure 5. Regarding the results for Cordoba, The T_{SA} values for DIEC and DW-DIEC were between 9.35–19.90 °C and 7.13–19.93 °C, see respectively Figure 4a and Figure 4b. The maximum T_{SA} values around 19.9 °C were similar for both advanced air-cooling systems. However, the minimum T_{SA} value was lower for DW-DIEC than for DIEC due the DW operation. The ω_{SA} values for DIEC and DW-DIEC were between 4.06–10.49 g·kg⁻¹ and 0.05–9.79 g·kg⁻¹, see respectively Figure 4a and Figure 4b. The maximum ω_{SA} values around 10 g·kg⁻¹ were similar for both advanced air-cooling systems. However, the minimum ω_{SA} value was 4.01 g·kg⁻¹ lower for DW-DIEC than for DIEC due the DW operation.

Figure 4. Outdoor air (OA) and supply air (SA) conditions for Cordoba and Malaga.

Regarding the SA values for Malaga, it can be observed that the T_{SA} values for DIEC and DW-DIEC ranged between 14.16–19.87 °C and 9.30–23.96 °C, see respectively in Figure 5a and in Figure 5b. The ω_{SA} values for DIEC and DW-DIEC were between 5.48–10.49 g·kg⁻¹ and 1.63–12.32 g·kg⁻¹, see respectively Figure 5a and Figure 5b. For DW-DIEC operating under the OA conditions of Malaga, the established set-point values (T_{SP} and ω_{SP}) were exceeded. The percentage of the period analysed for Malaga in which the T_{SA} value was higher than T_{SP} and the ω_{SA} value was higher than ω_{SP} was 19.7%, see yellow square in Figure 5b. This suggests that a DW with higher value of dehumidification capacity could be an interesting alternative for a new DW-DIEC system. However, adequate T_{SA} and ω_{SA} values were shown for DW-DIEC in Malaga.

Figure 5. Outdoor air (OA) and supply air (SA) conditions for Cordoba and Malaga.

The maximum and minimum ϵ_{dp} values for DIEC and DW-DIEC under the Cordoba and Malaga conditions are shown in Figure 6. The range of $\epsilon_{dp,DIEC}$ values in Cordoba was 0.08–0.92 and in Malaga was 0.10–0.83. Thus, the DIEC system showed a higher ϵ_{dp} value (0.92) than DW-DIEC (0.83) for the hot-dry climate zone of Cordoba. The range of $\epsilon_{dp,DW-DIEC}$ values in Cordoba was 0.21–0.71 and in Malaga was 0.37–0.99. Therefore, the DW-DIEC system showed a higher value of ϵ_{dp} (0.99) than the DIEC system (0.71) for the hot-humid climate zone of Malaga. The minimum $\epsilon_{dp,DW-DIEC}$ value for Malaga (0.37) was also higher than the minimum $\epsilon_{dp,DW-DIEC}$ value for Cordoba (0.21).

Figure 6. Dew-point efficiency (ϵ_{dp}) values for DIEC and DW-DIEC.

The main findings of this work were:

- Feasibility rate (FR). The FR of using DW-DIEC was 7.5% higher compared to DIEC for Cordoba weather conditions due to the DW humidity control in the DW-DIEC system. The FR of using DW-DIEC was 24.3% higher compared to DIEC for Malaga weather conditions due to the humidity control of DW in the DW-DIEC system and the high humidity values of the Malaga outdoor air.

- Supply air (SA) conditions. DIEC exhibited acceptable values of T_{SA} and ω_{SA} for both Cordoba and Malaga weather conditions, as did DW-DIEC. However, in 19.7% of the period analysed for DW-DIEC in Malaga, the T_{SA} value was higher than the T_{SP} value and the ω_{SA} value was higher than the ω_{SP} value.
- Dew-point efficiency (ϵ_{dp}). The highest ϵ_{dp} values were obtained for DIEC under the Cordoba weather conditions, $\epsilon_{dp,DIEC}$ of 0.92, and for DW-DIEC under the Malaga weather conditions, $\epsilon_{dp,DW-DIEC}$ of 0.99. The DW operation significantly influenced these values based on these values depending on the outdoor air humidity of the climate zone.

These results showed that the use of the DIEC system is feasible in hot-dry climate zones. On the other hand, the use of the DW-DIEC system is feasible in both hot-dry climate zones and hot-humid climate zones, a truly efficient solution under the climate change scenario.

4. Acknowledgment

The authors acknowledge the financial support received by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, through the research project WEDISTRIC, reference H2020-WIDESPREAD2018-03-857801.

5. References

Romero-Lara M.J., Comino F., Ruiz de Adana M. (2021), *Seasonal Analysis Comparison of Three Air-Cooling Systems in Terms of Thermal Comfort, Air Quality and Energy Consumption for School Buildings in Mediterranean Climates*. *Energies* 14(4436).

Romero-Lara M.J., Comino F., Ruiz de Adana M. (2022), *Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio of Regenerative Indirect Evaporative Coolers—Simplified Calculation Method*. *Applied Thermal Engineering* 220 (November 2022): 119710.

Yang H., Shi W., Chen Y., Min Y. (2021), *Research Development of Indirect Evaporative Cooling Technology: An Updated Review*. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 145(March): 111082.